

Ethno veterinary approaches on control and treating parasitic diseases

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ABSTRACT

In most African countries livestock contributes 30% of total agricultural gross domestic product. More than 60% of the population depends on agriculture for their livelihood. Parasitic worms or helminths occur worldwide parasitizing the body of humans and domesticated and wild animals. Conventional medicine is a remedy or drug used for the diagnosis, treatment of disease, and for maintenance of the health of an animal. Continuous use of these drugs has resulted in the development of resistance by some internal parasites. "The ability of parasites to survive doses of drugs that would normally kill parasites of the same species and stage." In general, most of the ethno-botanical remedies are considered as economical and safe. Furthermore, these remedies are easily available, simple to prepare and/or administer, at minute or free of cost to the farmer. Today many of the allopathic anthelmintics available in the market are either not effective or have induced resistance, resulting in the recurrence of parasitic infestations. External parasites affecting different animals are ticks, mites, lice, and fleas. Extract the active compounds from the medicinal plants and then test their anthelmintic activity, through *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems. Traditional medicine in Ethiopia has been widely used by various ethnic groups, about 90% of the livestock population depends on traditional medicine and most of it comes from plants. Herbal medicine has not been documented adequately in Ethiopia and there is a danger that this knowledge will soon be lost as traditional social patterns are increasingly disturbed by globalization, environmental degradation, agricultural expansion, cultivation of marginal lands, and urbanization.

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Introduction

In most African countries livestock contributes 30% of total agricultural gross domestic product [1]. More than 60% of the population depends on agriculture for their livelihood [2]. National Livestock Statistics [3] reported that livestock are useful for developing countries and their numbers are reportedly increasing in developing countries [4]. However, this may make clear evidence of the ability of stock to survive and produce in environments on low-cost feeds in developing countries [4].

In today's period of modernization, pollution and environmental degradation, livestock are also affected. They suffer because of various ailments

which affect their health and productivity. Medical facilities are available but are very costly and have side effects. The dairy persons, farmers, and livestock rearers mostly refuse to use allopathy drugs and prefer their own traditional practices of ethnoveterinary [5].

The application of traditional medicine to veterinary medicine has been termed ethnoveterinary medicine (EVM) which is mainly concerned with folk beliefs, knowledge, skills, methods and practices that are used in the healthcare of animals. It comprises traditional surgical techniques, traditional immunization, magicoreligious practices, and the use of herbal medicines to treat livestock diseases [6].

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The relationship between the use of medicinal plants in animals and humans is rather complex. However, an overlap in the use of plant remedies for the same indications in animals and human beings may occur, pointing to a theory that humans may have tried these remedies in animals before they used them for their own medical problems. Alternatively, humans may have used their overall arsenal of medicinal plants to treat animals, irrespective of whether or not they used the remedies themselves. Some evidence indicates that some animals may develop a natural attraction towards certain healing chemicals in plants [7].

Medicinal plants included in ethnobotanical and ethnoveterinary studies have become increasingly recognized as valuable sources for pharmacological studies. However, the most important problems encountered in herbal remedies are the lack of standardization of the active substance in the herbal preparations in terms of concentration and purity and the inability to control their side effects. More recently, the scientific evaluation of ethnobotanical knowledge has become much more common, particularly as a number of drug discovery studies have begun the regular screening of traditional herbal remedies [8].

Helminthiasis is one of the most important animal diseases worldwide, causing heavy production losses in grazing animals. It is prevalent in developing countries, mainly due to warm temperatures, in association with poor management practices and inadequate control measures [9]. This disease is caused by a range of internal parasites including roundworms, tapeworms, lungworms, and flukes [10].

Ethnoveterinary deworming preparations and the methods against helminth parasites of ruminants have been developed in developing countries [5].

Globally, research has been conducted on plant species as alternative anthelmintic drugs to manage gastrointestinal infections in livestock and several researchers reported the use of medicinal plants to be safe, sustainable, and environmentally acceptable, low cost relative to synthetic drugs, and the perceived better effective as compared to pharmaceuticals for chronic pathologies, as well as the presence of a mixture of active principles that could act in synergy, yielding the anthelmintic effect and limit the development of resistance [11].

These concerns have given impetus to the search for new drugs, with attention focusing on the search for plant products and the application of plant products as alternative methods of control. On the other hand, chemotherapeutic anthelmintic poses the problem of soil contamination, and also residual amounts of these anthelmintic may be found in the faces after treatment and these may have deleterious effects on the environment. Naturally produced plants offer an alternative that can overcome some of these problems and is both sustainable and environmentally acceptable. In response to the need to discover new anthelmintic drugs of natural origin with possibly low toxicity to host animals and also to raise them free from chemical inputs, there is a growing interest in ethno-medical and ethno-veterinary practices across the world [12].

In other words, when farmers face the challenge of scarcity, erratic supply, and/or prohibitive costs of synthetic drugs or veterinary services, and they usually revert back to more appropriate and sustainable traditional systems of animal health care [13]. In Africa and other developing countries, the use of EVM is proving to be successful. Around 80% of the marginalized people in the world depend on traditional medicine for controlling and treating various diseases affecting human beings and animals [14].

There is, therefore, a need to gather this ethnoveterinary knowledge to review this ethno-veterinary healing and conserve it through systematic studies before it is lost forever [15].

Therefore, the objective of this article is a feature on reviewing ethno-veterinary performance must be determined by sciences. Due to parasitic diseases the most abundant in landmasses and causing worldwide complications in animals through wasting progressively body conditions up to the loss of life, furtherly by the declining economy of the nation-state. Currently, with increasing manpower of veterinarians and veterinary professionals particularly in developing countries including community animal health workers (CAHWs) in every village at least there is one or above animal health profession or CAHWs especially in pastoralists area contested for business in the community during treated animals for both internal and external parasites without history taking from the owners that devastate the increment of conventional anthelmintic drugs to develop anthelmintic resistance and knowledge of ethno-veterinary become reduced in practices. Until new conventional medications are generated,

traditional medicinal herbs will lessen the hazards associated with the fatal case of anthelmintic or antimicrobial resistance caused by conventional drugs correlated with them. Government emphasis on the need to safeguard medicinal plants is also necessary.

- To review anthelmintics resistance against conventional drugs.
- To review the ethno-veterinary practices regarding parasitic.
- To review the threats weighing on traditional herbal medicine.

Literature Review

Review on parasitic diseases and their economic impact

A parasite is an organism that lives in or on another and takes its nourishment from that other organism, or "host." Parasites of animals and humans come in many forms, including helminths (worms), arthropods (lice, ticks, mosquitoes, etc.), and protozoa. There are over 1,000 species of parasites affecting domesticated animals throughout the world. They can be broadly classified as external or internal, depending on where they live on their host [16].

Parasitic worms or helminths occur worldwide parasitizing the body of humans and domesticated and wild animals [17]. They often belong to the phyla Platyhelminths (flatworms), including the trematodes and cestodes, and Nematoda (roundworms) [18]. Helminth infections are causing major health problems for humans and are considered among the major public health concerns throughout the globe [19]. However, helminthiasis are arguably of even greater relative importance in our domestic animals. Generally, helminth infections have the impact of decreased productivity in livestock animals through: (a) damage to the infected tissues, leading to decreased performance of the affected organ; (b) consuming the energy that is supposed to be utilized in production in immune and defense mechanisms; and (c) a decrease in feed consumption [20].

Helminth infections are an important group of diseases in grazing ruminants affecting their health conditions and productivity. Parasitic nematodes have major economic impacts on livestock throughout the world [21]. The economic impacts of parasites on livestock may be divided into two groups (direct and indirect impacts). Direct

impacts are those attributable purely to the presence of the parasite, e.g., reduced economic productivity of the livestock or economic loss due to mortality. Indirect impacts occur because some parasites, such as ticks, are also disease vectors, and vector-borne diseases, if transmitted to a livestock host, often result in much greater economic loss than the presence of the parasite. Furthermore, by weakening the host the presence of a parasite may make the animal much more susceptible to infection and adverse impact from other diseases, or to environmental stresses such as food deficits [22].

Parasitic disease management using conventional drugs

Conventional medicine is a remedy or drug used for the diagnosis, treatment of disease, and for the maintenance of the health of an animal [23]. Phytotherapy is either prophylactical or therapeutic use of plants, their plant components, or their preparations, and can be divided into allopathic and traditional phytotherapy. The allopathic phytotherapeutic approach uses scientific testing to verify the anthelmintic effectiveness of a plant or preparation, and in contrast to that the use of traditional products is based on handed-down knowledge [24]. Parasitic infestations reduced productivity in livestock, particularly in poor worldwide. Phytomedicine has been used traditionally to treat parasitism and improve the performance of livestock. Scientific validation of the anti-parasitic effects and possible side effects of plant products in animals is necessary prior to their approval for parasite control [25]. In many African societies, both conventional and traditional healing practices exist alongside each other. Normally people consult both systems; the availability of a conventional veterinarian and the disease concerned are factors that determine whether an ethnovegetative or conventional treatment is chosen [26].

Internal parasites are controlled by drugs that belong to three families namely benzimidazoles, nicotinic, and macrolytic lactones [27]. Benzimidazoles such as albendazole and oxbendazole are also known as white dewormers and are active against tapeworms, roundworms (trichostrongyles) and liver flukes (*Fasciola hepatica*) [28]. Macrolytic lactones are chemical derivatives of soil microorganisms of the genus *Streptomyces* which are active against immature nematodes and arthropods [29]. Nicotinic are effective against cestodes and trematodes [30]. Some of these drugs are specific to

Table 1. Anti-parasitic drug classes and their actions [27,30].

Class	Active ingredient (drug)	Action
Macrocyclic lactones	Moxidectin, ivermectin, doramectin	Effective against all helminths, interfere with the GABA-mediated neurotransmission, thereby killing and paralyzing parasites
Benzimidazole	Thiabendazole, albendazole, mebendazole, fenbendazole, oxfendazole	Effective against tapeworms, roundworms, and flukes interfere with the worm's metabolism by binding to the block (beta tubulin) thereby preventing its incorporation into microtubules.
Nicotinics	Levamisole, morantel, pyrantel	Effective against cestodes and trematodes. Mimic the activity of acetylcholine that initiates muscle contraction and the worm will not be able to feed.

particular parasites, whereas some have a broad spectrum effect. Drenching of goats using these drugs is usually done on a monthly basis to cut the life cycle of worms, which takes an average of 21 days [31]. Continuous use of these drugs has resulted in the development of resistance by some internal parasites. Ticks and mites are usually controlled by acaricides which are applied in different ways. Acaricides can be applied by dipping, pour on, and spraying [32]. Fleas are controlled by insecticides which are formulated as dust sprays or fine sprays [33]. Anti-tick vaccines have also been developed, and are environmentally friendly [34]. Ivermectin can be used to control parasites such as ticks, fleas, and mites. Parasites have developed resistance against some of the acaricides which makes tick control difficult. For example, *Boophilus* ticks are resistant to organophosphate carbonate [28].

Another problem is that commercial insecticides are expensive and most resource-limited farmers cannot afford to buy them. Commercial drugs tend to indiscriminately kill beneficial insects and birds thereby affecting the food chain [34]. Table 1 shows the common three families of drugs used to control internal parasites.

Drug resistance against anti-parasitic drugs

The definition of resistance varies in different publications. The following definition is given in the "Guideline on anthelmintic combination products targeting nematode infections of ruminants and horses" published by the World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary Parasitology [35]. The crises of drug resistance in parasites that cause different diseases in animals necessitate developing new sources of the drug to overcome failure therapy. Such parasites cover a broad phylogenetic range and include protozoa, helminths, and arthropods. In order to achieve effective parasite control in the future, the identification and diagnosis of resistance will be essential [25]. AR is a heritable

loss of sensitivity of an anthelmintic in a parasite population that was in the past susceptible to the same anthelmintic. It is considered that AR is present when a higher proportion of the parasite individuals within a population are able to lose sensitivity to doses of an anthelmintic than in a normal population of the same species and it is transmitted from generation to generation [36].

Control of gastrointestinal nematodes in livestock generally uses broad-spectrum anthelmintic such as benzimidazole, probenzimidazole, imidazothiazole, macrolide and ivermectin. The widespread use of several anthelmintic groups currently causes an increase in the incidence of gastrointestinal nematodes against anthelmintics so that it is necessary to control them regularly and periodically for livestock. At present the resistance to the benzimidazole class anthelmintic has occurred almost all over the world and its prevalence continues to increase from year to year. This is evidenced by the large number of studies and cases in the field regarding the prevalence of resistance of nematodes to benzimidazole anthelmintics [37].

The development of AR is evident in different helminths of almost every animal species and in different groups of anthelmintic on several continents [38]. Broad spectrum anthelmintics which are most commonly used for the treatment of livestock GIT helminth infection in Ethiopia fall under the three anthelmintic families, which are benzimidazoles (e.g., albendazole and triclabendazole), imidazothiazoles (like tetramisole and levamisole) and macrocyclic lactones (e.g., ivermectin). Unregulated and inappropriate anthelmintic use contributed to the failure to abate livestock gastrointestinal parasitism, and instead resulted in the appearance of AR in various nematode parasites under different geographical areas in Ethiopia [39].

Table 2 gives an overview of the mechanisms of resistance formation using anthelmintic drugs extensively.

Table 2. Shows the mechanisms of resistance formation using anthelmintic drugs extensively.

<i>Anthelmintic class</i>	<i>Drug example</i>	<i>Anthelmintic spectrum</i>	<i>Proposed mechanism of resistance formation</i>	<i>References</i>
Benzimidazoles	Albendazole, albendazole dan, fenbendazole, oxfendazole	GIT nematodes of ruminants	Some mutations in the β -tubulin isotype-1 gene. substitution of phenylalanine for tyrosine at positions codons 167 and 200 (F167Y and F200Y) of isotype-1-tubulin and acid substitution glutamate for alanine at position 198 (E198A)	[37]
Probenzimidazoles	Febantel, netobimin	GI and lung nematodes of many host species, liver flukes, tapeworms	Mutation in the gene coding for β -tubulin isotype 1	[41]
Imidazothiazoles Tetrahydropyrimidines	Levamisole, pyrantel	GIT nematodes of ruminants	Reduced expression levels of genes coding for nACh sub-units, which make up the receptor, have been linked to the drug	[39]
Amino-acetonitrile derivatives	Monepantel	GI and lung nematodes of ruminants	Loss of part of nAChR superfamily member ACR-23	[42,43]
Macrocyclic lactones: Avermectins Milbemycins	Ivermectin and moxidectin	GIT nematodes of ruminants	An allele of a GluCl α -subunit gene was found more often, implying that a mutation in this gene was linked and P-glycoproteins serve as an efflux mechanism to transport molecules across the cell membrane thus lowering their intracellular concentration	[39]

Parasites have developed resistance against some of the acaricides which makes tick control difficult. The prolonged or incorrect use of tick chemicals can lead to resistance in ticks, enabling the ticks to tolerate and survive chemical applications [40]. Acaricide resistance has become widespread in countries where cattle ticks, *Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) microplus*, are a problem. Resistance arises through genetic changes in a cattle tick population that causes modifications to the target site, increased metabolism or sequestration of the acaricide, or reduced ability of the acaricide to penetrate through the outer protective layers of the tick's body [44].

Medicinal plants as a major solution for parasitic resistance

Ethno-botanical remedies are economical and safe. Furthermore, these remedies are easily available, simple to prepare and/or administer, at minute or free of cost to the farmer [45], and even considered as the best healing agents for the treatment of parasitic diseases [46].

Medicinal plants used to treat helminth parasite

Unfortunately, intensive use or overuse of anthelmintics, insufficient dosing, repeated treatment, and incorrect drug administration routes contribute to the development of selective pressure on the parasites. The increasing resistance of pathogenic gastrointestinal parasites to available anthelmintics

is an important veterinary and economic concern [47]. The medicinal properties of plant species have made an exceptional input to the beginning and improvement of many conventional healthcare systems. Thus, there has recently been a resurgence of interest in the development of drugs from plants, especially from those of developing countries that have a rich heritage of botanical ethno-pharmacopoea [48].

Medicinal plants are believed to have compounds in their leaves, seeds, fruits, and inflorescence for medicinal purposes [49]. They possess a range of pharmacologically active phytochemical compounds which include alkaloids, glycosides, resins, volatile oils, and tannins [50]. In developing countries, most communal people are now using plants due to their low cost and effectiveness. This has led researchers to validate these medicinal plants reported in various countries [51]. As defined by the anthropologist McCorkle [52], EVM comprises a multifaceted system of beliefs, practices, knowledge, and skills relevant to animal husbandry as well as general animal care. Across the world, many plants with anthelmintic activity have been discovered and there are many published reports on these plants [53].

Consequently, herbal drugs were extensively used worldwide as anthelmintics before the introduction of modern broad-spectrum pharmacological agents. Further, certain modern anthelmintics are derived from naturally occurring plants or their synthetic analogs [47]. In order to use effective parasite control

Table 3. Some plants used to control internal parasites [25].

Plant name	Scientific name	Secondary bioactive metabolites	Uses
Nematodes garlic bulb	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Thiosulfinates, such as allicin	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i> in goats and sheep
Walnut leaves and peels	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	Naphthoquinone	Nematodes
Chicory forage	<i>Cichorium intybus</i> L.	Terpenoids or phenolic compounds coumarins	Lungworm in deers, <i>Ostertagia ostertagi</i> in cattle, GIT nematode in lambs
Wormseed	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Ascaridole	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i> in goats
Coccidiosis garlic bulb	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Allicin	<i>Eimeria ninakohlyakimovae</i> in goats and hepatic coccidiosis in rabbits
Pine bark	<i>Pinus radiata</i> D. Don	Tannins	<i>Eimeria tenella</i> , <i>Eimeria maxima</i> , and <i>Eimeria acervulina</i>
Green tea	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L.) Kuntze	Polyphenolic compounds	Inactivate the enzymes for coccidian sporulation
Barberry root bark	<i>Berberis lycium</i> Royle	Isoquinoline alkaloid berberine	Inhibition of the sporozoites of <i>E. tenella</i> in chickens via induction of oxidative stress
Guar bean	<i>Cyamopsis tetragonoloba</i> L. Taub	Saponins which could lyse oocysts	Suppression of coccidiosis in chickens
Olive tree	<i>Olea europaea</i> L.	Maslinic acid	Increases the anticoccidial index
Grape seed	<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.	Proanthocyanidin	Diminishes coccidiosis via downregulation of oxidative stress
Turmeric rhizome	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Curcumin (diferuloylmethane)	Destroyed sporozoites of <i>E. tenella</i> and diminished gut damage in poultry
Coneflowers	<i>Echinacea purpurea</i> (L.) Moench	Flavonoid echinolone chicoric acid	Elicit humoral immune response against coccidial infection in chickens
Aloe leaves	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Acemann sugars anthraquinones	Aloe vera-supplemented group showed significantly fewer intestinal lesions

via medicinal plants in the future, the identification of their bioactive metabolites will be crucial.

Table 3 gives the summary of different antiparasitic plants with their bioactive compounds and uses.

Medicinal plants used to treat ecto-parasites

External parasites are organisms that live on the surface of their host's epidermis, to shelter and feed [54]. External parasites affecting different animals are ticks, mites, lice, and fleas. They are a threat to livestock production [55].

They damage the skin and other subcutaneous tissue. Moreover, they feed on body tissue such as blood causing wounds and discomfort to the animal. Skin damage as a result of ecto-parasites infection causes huge losses to the tanning industry [56]. Ticks transmit protozoan, viral, and rickettsial diseases. Diseases such as babesiosis, anaplasmosis, and heartwater are major constraints in the production and development of livestock and cause great losses to the livestock industry [57]. External parasites feed on body tissue such as blood, skin, and hair. The wounds and skin irritation produced by

these parasites result in discomfort and irritation to the animal. Parasites can transmit diseases from sick to healthy animals. They can reduce weight gain and milk production. In general, infested livestock cannot be efficiently managed [58].

In small ruminants, *Veronia conferia* (leaves), palm oil, and engine oil are used against fleas, ticks and mange, respectively in Nigeria [59]. In South Africa *Aloe ferox*, *Acokanthera oppositifolia* and *Elephantorrhiza elephantina* were the plants having the highest fidelity level for their use to control parasites [60]. Table 4 indicates some medicinal plants used to treat external parasites in East Africa.

Methods of assessing medicinal value of medicinal plants

The effects that parasitized hosts experience as a consequence of plant consumption result from interactions between the nutritional values and the pharmacological or medicinal properties of the plants. In order to facilitate the validation process of medicinal plants, there is a concurrent trend towards using plant extracts. Extraction procedures used for this purpose vary from simple water

Table 4. Some medicinal plants used to control external parasite in East Africa [63].

Plant part	Scientific name	Uses	Animal type treated
Leaves	<i>Aloe secundiflora</i> , <i>Ajuga remota</i> , <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Effective against ticks	Treatment for all animals
Seed	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>		
Root	<i>Adenium obesum</i>	Effective against fleas	Treatment for all animals
Leaves	<i>Aloe secundiflora</i>		
Leaves	<i>Tephrosia vogelii</i>		
Bulbs	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Effective against lice	Cattle, goats, sheep
Leaves and soft twigs	<i>Tagetes minuta</i>		
Fresh seed	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Effective against biting flies	Treatment for cows, goats, sheep, donkeys, camels
Leaves	<i>Aloe secundiflora</i>		Treatment for sheep, goats, camels and cattle
Fresh fruit	<i>Juniperus procera</i>	Effective against mites	Cattle, goats, sheep
Leaves, bark and branches	<i>Salvadora persica</i>		Treatment for camels, cattle, donkeys, goats and sheep

extractions to very complicated ones, where a series of organic solvents is used [61]. The aim is to extract the active compounds from the medicinal plants and then test their anthelmintic activity, through *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems. The anthelmintic properties of several medicinal plant extracts have been evaluated through *in vitro* systems and their efficiencies have in some cases approached 100% [62].

When using plant extracts to assess the anthelmintic activity of medicinal plants, it relates the concentration of the active compound in the extract and that found in the plant. The plant extract, as obtained following the extraction process, will inevitably have a high concentration of the active compounds, in most cases, this will not correspond to the concentration of the active compounds consumed by parasitized hosts when the plant is included in their diets [64].

A variety of methods has been explored to validate the anthelmintic properties of such plant remedies, both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. The main advantages of using *in vitro* assays to test for the anti-parasitic activities of essential oils and extracts from plants are the low expenses and rapid results which permit the screening of large numbers of samples. It has been suggested that the consumption of some plants may be associated with an enhanced immune response of the host towards the parasites, as a result of nutrient supplementation and thus improved nutrition. It is known that high dietary protein intake in animals can enhance the immune response of ruminants towards parasites. *In vivo* studies are more applicable and reliable than *in vitro* studies, although large-scale

screening of plant extracts is more expensive. The *in vivo* methods normally have parasitized hosts being treated with known doses of extracts compared with untreated controls and standard anthelmintic drugs. However, in most cases the active material has to be extracted from the plant and *in vitro* conditions and concentrations used are not always comparable to those *in vivo*, and thus often the results can differ in the two assays [25].

Furthermore, *in vitro* models are often used to validate plant extracts, without the simultaneous use of *in vivo* experimentation. Although *in vitro* testing of the antiparasitic properties of plant extracts offers the opportunity to screen large numbers of plant extracts at low cost and rapid turnover, *in vitro* results are not always verified by *in vivo* experimentation and it is often questionable whether the *in vitro* assays are relevant to *in vivo* conditions [65]. However, concentrations of potentially active substances used *in vitro* do not always correspond to *in vivo* bioavailability. Hence, further *in vivo* study is required to enlighten the therapeutic potential of plant extracts in treating helminth infection. The *in vivo* assay such as fecal egg count reduction test is suitable for the evaluation of all types of anthelmintics [66].

The usage of plant anthelmintics to combat gastrointestinal helminths of small ruminants is well documented by several parasitologists [67]. Atanine, a quinolone alkaloid extracted from *Evodia rutaecarpa* dried fruits. *In vitro* tests demonstrated inhibition of motility of free-living stages of the trematode *Schistoma mansoni*, and against the

nematodes *Caenorhabditis elegans* adult stage and larvae of *Teladorsagia circumcincta* [68], mangiferin, a major polyphenol in the aqueous extract vimang acquired from *Mangifera indica*. The polyphenol and the aqueous extract were tested in an *in vivo* mouse model against enteric and parenteral stages of *Trichinella spiralis*. Moderate effects were reported against the larval stages in the muscles but not against adult parasites [69] and flavan-3-ols (the monomer units of CT), and their galloyl derivatives were evaluated *in vitro* on the viability of eggs, the development and the viability of the free living stages of the sheep nematode *Trichostrongylus colubriformis*. The flavan-3-ol was found to have an effect on egg hatching as well as the development of larvae [70]. Aqueous and various solvent extracts viz. hexane, chloroform, ethylacetate, alcoholic extracts, pastes, essential oils, extracted from leaves, stems, fruits, flowers, and roots or whole plants were used to test their anthelmintic efficacy *in vitro* or *in vivo*.

Medicinal plants used to treat parasitic diseases in Ethiopia

Ethiopia is believed to be home to about 6,000 species of higher plants with approximately 10% endemism [71]. Traditional medicine in Ethiopia has been widely used by various ethnic groups, about 90% of livestock population depends on traditional medicine and most of it comes from plants [72]. Chemotherapeutic control practices have led to a number of problems, the resistance of helminths to various groups of anthelmintic [73]. The major anthelmintic drugs commonly used in Ethiopia for the control of helminths parasites in small ruminants are benzimidazoles (albendazole, triclabendazole, fenbendazole), levamisole (tetramisole) and oxcyclozanide. Since country-wide surveys for anthelmintic resistance have not yet been carried out, the current prevalence of anthelmintic resistance in Ethiopia might be underestimated. In addition to anthelmintic resistance, inadequate availability and high cost of commercial anthelmintics are the other important constraints of helminth control in developing countries. This problem has drawn the attention of researchers to the development of alternative methods for treating helminthosis. In Ethiopia, some traditional healers and most farmers use medicinal plants for the treatment of various animal health problems including treatment of helminth infections [74].

According to Belina et al. [75], the report revealed that 24.17% of farmers they interviewed in Ethiopia use medicinal plants against helminths.

Crude aqueous and hydroalcoholic extracts of leaves *Myrsine africana*, *Rhus glabrous*, *Jasminum abyssinicum*, *Rhus vulgaris*, *Acokantheras chimperi*, and aerial parts of *Foeniculum vulgare* were screened for possible anthelmintic activity against nematode *Haemonchus contortus*. *Myrsine africana*, (Myrsinaceae), kurjan seed (Eng) locally called “Kechemo” (Amharic) are used as anthelmintics in Ethiopia. It is particularly effective for the expulsion of the tapeworms in other ways decoctions of the leaves are used as blood purifiers [76].

Medicinal plants and knowledge of their use provide a vital contribution to human and livestock health care needs throughout the country. Such plants include *Phytolaccado decandra* and many species of *Maytenus* [74]. The therapeutic value of *Achyranthes aspera* is known for skin diseases and various gastrointestinal and respiratory problems in livestock, especially ruminants [77]. The medicinal plant *Azadirachta indica* is used to treat endo-parasite and ecto-parasites in livestock especially ruminants in the Borena pastoralists, southern Ethiopia [78]. Moreover, the efficacy of leaves of *Azadirachta indica* to reduce the parasitic load and that of the *Aloe* species in treating *Trychostrongylus* in sheep and it contain chemicals that could help to control more than 200 pest species as well as antimalarial limuloids that showed good antimalarial [79].

Kosso (*Hagenia abyssinica*) “Grawa” (*Vernonia amygdalina*) and “mixed roots and leaves” were the most frequently believed to be efficacious against gastrointestinal parasites for use in donkeys, cattle and small ruminants [80]. In some parts of the country, livestock diseases such as anthrax (quruba), black leg (aba gurba), anaplasmosis (afreera), ascariasis (wosfat), abscess (ebach), leeches (alqt), trypanosomiasis, lymphangitis (gubgub), stomatitis (yafqusil), and coccidiosis (fengel) have been treated using various natural plant product combinations [81].

Vulnerabilities for medicinal plants

Nature is full of undiscovered medicines and valuable chemicals that can potentially be used in healthcare systems and save countless lives [82]. People around the world collect or use medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) for treating and preventing illnesses. The World Health Organization has acknowledged the importance of traditional medicines, and particularly in many developing countries, where around 70%–95% of the population rely on these medicines for primary care. Medicinal plants form the basis for these healthcare systems. Most active

mechanisms in modern pharmaceutical drugs were either directly or indirectly derived from natural products, which include plants and other life forms. This still holds despite the advent of synthetic and combinatorial chemistry. Moreover, MAPs and their specimens are used in cosmetics, food, and luxury products. Approximately 60,000 MAP species are harvested globally, of which around 1,280 are estimated to be listed in CITES Appendices [83].

Despite the aforementioned facts; information on veterinary herbal medicine has not been documented adequately in Ethiopia and there is a danger that this knowledge will soon be lost as traditional social patterns are increasingly disturbed by globalization [84], environmental degradation, agricultural expansion, cultivation of marginal lands and urbanization [85] warranting an urgent need to document and preserve the indigenous knowledge. So transmission of the knowledge by documenting and preserving it for the next generation is the most valuable work and can also be used as a vital tool to conduct pharmacological tests on plants [86].

Like all living members of the biosphere, climate change affects the life cycle and distributions of MAPs. These changes are likely to affect plant ecology, e.g., drought and heat wave effects on photosynthesis, respiration, and transpiration [87] and increase plant mortality and extinction risk in many areas [88]. Due to climate change, some medicinal plants move to higher latitudes and some medicinal plants become extinct [88].

Conclusions and Recommendations

Parasites cause disease and production loss in livestock, causing economic loss and impacting animal welfare. Control measures are costly and time-consuming. Resistance to conventional medicines is a concern, as they are not effective for animal health and economic impacts. People far from urban areas use medicinal plants for effective control and treatment, as they possess active phytochemical compounds and are distributed throughout the continents without education.

Based on the above conclusion, the following recommendations are forwarded.

- Educate the public about the importance of medicinal plants in preventing damage to homes and other small items.
- The government has to prioritize safeguarding the medicinal plants that have been

traditionally used to cure various diseases, including parasitic infections.

- It is important to record and write down the traditional knowledge that different practitioners have about ethnoveterinary medicinal plants.
- The promotion and integration of research, training, and application necessitate strong policy support.
- Additionally, the use of medicinal plants to treat livestock diseases needs to be examined and scientifically investigated.

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